

ON BLIND FRACTIONALLY-SPACED EQUALIZATION USING ANALYTICAL CONSTANT MODULUS

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ABSTRACT

In this contribution we discuss the applicability of the so-called analytical constant modulus approach to the case of blind fractionally-spaced equalization of communication channels. We demonstrate that such an approach cannot be pursued when the equalizer is straightforwardly parameterized by the samples of its FIR impulse response. Then, we obtain a new parameterization of the equalizer, exploiting the modulation redundancy associated to the excess bandwidth usually available in fractionally sampled PAM and QAM signals. It is pointed out that the FIR equalizer belongs to properly defined linear subspace, related to the geometrical structure of a suitable matrix build up using time-varying correlations of the received signal. Exploiting this new parameterization, we finally show that the analytical constant modulus approach is successfully applicable in blind fractionally-spaced equalization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Blind design of equalizers of communication channels is successfully achieved by proper exploitation of the Constant Modulus (CM) property of the constellation from which the transmitted symbols are drawn.

In the most popular techniques, such as the CM algorithm [1], [2] or the Super Exponential (SE) algorithm [3], the equalizer is recursively updated on the basis of certain higher order statistics (HOS) that, more or less explicitly, measure the deviation from the CM property of the equalized output. (In [4], [5], reviews of the state of art of CM based equalization are found while a description of the SE algorithm is found in [3]).

A different technique is described in [6], where the CM criterion, therein employed in the blind separation of sources carried by plane waves and impinging on an array of sensors, is analytically treated so to derive the CM beamformer in a closed form, resorting to a special technique of constrained minimization. Similar approaches have been used in [7] and [8] in the case of blind channel equalization at symbol rate.

In this contribution, we will transpose the developments in [6] to the case of blind fractionally spaced equalization. First, we will show the general inapplicability of the straightforward extension of the analytical CM method to fractionally-spaced equalization. Second, we will illustrate a particular analytical CM solution obtained resorting to a suitable equalizer parameterization that originates from the redundancy associated to

the excess bandwidth available in PAM and QAM modulation schemes.

This modulation redundancy has been exploited, in the recent past, by several blind parametric channel identification schemes (see the very recently appeared special issue [9]) among which we recall the cyclostationary random processes approach (Gardner's first contribution is [10]), the multichannel filtering approach (an early remarkable contribution is [11]), and the recent paper [12], which enlightens in a lucid fashion how equalization may be conducted using such a modulation redundancy.

The technique here described employs the modulation redundancy directly in the equalizer design. We will see that the equalizer is linearly constrained to belong to a suitable subspace related to the geometrical structure of the Sylvester matrix build up with the samples of the fractionally-sampled received signal.

Adopting this linear equalizer parameterization, we will prove the applicability of the analytical CM method to fractionally-spaced equalization. Moreover, as a side effect, we will see that the resulting method has a reduced computational burden due to the parsimony of the adopted equalizer parameterization.

Simulation results show that the accuracy of the resulting novel equalization scheme favorably compares to the accuracy of classical CM algorithms.

2. ANALYTICAL CONSTANT MODULUS FOR BLIND FRACTIONALLY-SPACED EQUALIZATION

The noisy signal received in a (two-times) fractionally sampled transmission system using Pulse Amplitude Modulation can be expressed as follows

$$y[n] = \sum_l s[l]h[n-2l] + v[n] \quad (1)$$

where the information symbols are denoted by $s[n]$ and the additive noise by $v[n]$. For the sake of comprehension, all the filters in the transmitter and in the receiver are incorporated together with the channel denoting the resulting overall impulse response by $h[n]$.

The estimated symbols after FIR equalization through the filter $f[n]$ are given by

$$\hat{s}[n] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (y * f)[2n] = \sum_{m=0}^{L-1} f[m]y[2n-m]$$

The CM criterion is written, without loss of generality,

$$J_{\text{CM}}(y; f) = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left[\left| \hat{s}[n] \right|^2 - 1 \right]^2 \right\}$$

and its minimization w.r.t. the equalizer coefficients will result in highly nonlinear (third order) equations.

Following the guidelines of [6], a different approach consists in taking as unknowns the products

$$\phi[m_1, m_2] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} f[m_1] \overline{f[m_2]} \quad (2)$$

that appear in the CM criterion, now written as follows

$$J_{\text{CM}}(y; \phi) =$$

$$\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left[\sum_{m_1=0}^{L-1} \sum_{m_2=0}^{L-1} \phi[m_1, m_2] y[2n - m_1] \overline{y[2n - m_2]} - 1 \right]^2 \right\}$$

Then, the minimization of $J_{\text{CM}}(y; \phi)$ can be conducted w.r.t. the unknowns $\phi[m_1, m_2]$ under the separability constraint (2).

Differentiating $J_{\text{CM}}(y; \phi)$ w.r.t. $\phi[k_1, k_2]$ and equating to zero yields the following L^2 normal-like equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial J_{\text{CM}}(y; \phi)(y; \phi)}{\partial \phi[k_1, k_2]} &= \sum_{m_1=0}^{L-1} \sum_{m_2=0}^{L-1} \phi[m_1, m_2] \\ &\cdot \mathbb{E} \left\{ y[2n - m_1] \overline{y[2n - m_2]} y[2n - k_2] \overline{y[2n - k_1]} \right\} \\ &- \mathbb{E} \left\{ y[2n - k_2] \overline{y[2n - k_1]} \right\} = 0 \quad ; \quad k_1, k_2 = 0, \dots, L-1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For the sake of compactness, let us define:

- the vector of unknowns $\|\phi\|_{m_1+Lm_2} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \phi[m_1, m_2]$;
- the vector of known terms (time varying correlations) $\|\mathbf{r}_y\|_{k_1+Lk_2} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{E} \left\{ y[2n - k_2] \overline{y[2n - k_1]} \right\}$;
- the matrix of coefficients (fourth order time varying moments)

$$\|\mathcal{C}_y\|_{k_1+Lk_2, m_1+Lm_2} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{E} \left\{ y[2n - m_1] \overline{y[2n - m_2]} y[2n - k_2] \overline{y[2n - k_1]} \right\}$$

so to rewrite (3) as follows

$$\mathcal{C}_y \phi = \mathbf{r}_y \quad (4)$$

In general, the rank of $\mathcal{C}_y$ is not sufficient to assure the uniqueness of the solution of (4), and thus ϕ must be searched in the kernel of $\mathcal{C}_y$ under the separability constraint (2).

In [6], an analytical technique to obtain the linearly independent, constrained to be separable, solutions of (4) is described. The applicability of this technique is limited to the case when the number of constrained, linearly independent solutions equals the nullity of $\mathcal{C}_y$ plus 1. A significantly large computational load is required since this analytical approach needs to perform a Super Generalized Schur Decomposition of matrices of dimensions $L \times L$.

In the case of fractional sampling, the following Proposition states that, for FIR channels of length $2M$, the number of structured solution is not sufficiently high and the analytical technique of [6] cannot be straightforwardly applied.

Let $K \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} L - M + 2$.

PROPOSITION 1

The nullity of $\mathcal{C}_y$ plus 1 is $N_S = K(2L - K + 1) + 2L(K - 1)$ and the number of linearly independent, constrained solutions of (4) is $N_{\text{SS}} = K(2L - K + 1)$.

Proof: see [13].

To overcome this limitation, a new equalizer parameterization will be derived in the next section by exploiting the modulation redundancy of fractionally sampled PAM and QAM signals.

3. REDUNDANCY INTRODUCED BY LINEAR MODULATION

Referring to the expanded sequence of symbols $a[n]$, defined as $a[2n] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} s[n]$, $a[2n+1] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 0$, the received signal (1) is also usefully expressed by means of discrete-time convolution

$$y[n] = \sum_m a[m] h[n - m] + v[n] = (a * h)[n] + v[n]$$

The redundancy introduced in the modulation process is well understood looking at the spectrum of the expanded symbols

$$A(e^{j\omega}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_m a[m] e^{-j\omega m} = \sum_l s[l] e^{-j\omega 2l} = A(e^{j\omega + j\pi})$$

which results periodic modulo π . Loosely speaking, the same useful ‘‘information’’ carried out by the symbols is allocated in both the frequency bands ($|\omega| < \pi/2$) and ($\pi/2 < |\omega| < \pi$) in a sort of ‘‘spectral diversity’’.¹

It is well know that, when the channel $h[n]$ is described by a rational transfer function and it has not zeros equispaced on a circle (*identifiability condition*), it is possible to find Zero Forcing (ZF) equalizers $f[n]$ of finite length, namely FIR filters of (great enough) length L , such that it results, for $\sigma_v^2 = 0$,

$$(y * f)[2n] = s[n] \quad (5)$$

This is equivalent to say that

$$(y * f)[n] = (a * d)[n] \quad (6)$$

where $d[n] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (h * f)[n]$ is overall channel+equalizer response, satisfying the zero Inter Symbol Interference (ISI) condition

$$D(e^{j\omega}) + D(e^{j\omega + j\pi}) = e^{-j\omega q}$$

¹Strictly speaking, when the symbols $s[n]$ are drawn from a stationary series, the received signal $y[n]$ is a member of a cyclostationary process. In particular, we define the complex time varying correlations as follows

$$R_y[n, k] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{E} \{ y[n] \overline{y[n - k]} \}$$

where an overbar denotes complex conjugation.

Fig. 1: Fractionally-sampled receiver scheme

where $D(e^{j\omega}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathcal{F}\{d[n]\}$ is the discrete-time Fourier transform of the sequence $d[n]$, and q is a suitable integer.

The ZF equalization problem is solved when a pair $f[n], d[n]$ is determined according to some optimality criterion.

In the following, we will show how the modulation redundancy can be exploited to obtain a homogeneous linear set of equations in the unknowns of the equalizer coefficients $f[n]$.

Toward this end, let us introduce the (ISI free) filter described by the following impulse response

$$d^\pi[n] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{D(e^{j\omega+j\pi})\} = (-1)^n d[n]$$

Then, let us convolve both members of (6) by $d^\pi[n]$ so to obtain, for $\sigma_v^2=0$,

$$\zeta[n] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (z * f)[n] = (a * d * d^\pi)[n] \quad (7)$$

where the signal $z[n]$ is observed at the output of the filter $d^\pi[n]$, i.e. $z[n] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (y * d^\pi)[n]$ (see also Fig.1).

Due to the inherent periodicity modulo π of $A(e^{j\omega})$ and of the product $D(e^{j\omega})D(e^{j\omega+j\pi})$, the odd indexed samples of both members of (7) are zero, i.e.²

$$\zeta[2n+1] = \sum_{m=0}^{L-1} f[m]z[2n+1-m] = 0 \quad (8)$$

Substantially these homogeneous equations express the fact that, in absence of noise, the finite length equalizer $f[n]$ belongs to a properly defined linear subspace of $\mathbb{C}^L$, i.e. the kernel of the coefficient matrix in (8).³

In this subspace, the equalizer is represented as follows

$$\mathbf{f} = \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \mathbf{b}_i \quad (9)$$

²The deterministic condition (8) can be also written in terms of time varying correlations: multiplying both members by $\bar{z}[2n+1-k]$ and taking expectation, we have

$$\sum_{m=0}^{L-1} f[m] \mathbb{E}\{z[2n+1-m] \bar{z}[2n+1-k]\} = \sum_{m=0}^{L-1} f[m] R_z[1-m, k-m] = 0$$

³Despite the fact that, in general, the rank of (8) could be not sufficient to ensure the uniqueness of the solution, subspace fitting based procedures, similar to that described in [14] for estimation of FIR channel parameters, can be devised to estimate the equalizer coefficients $f[m]$.

where the vector $\mathbf{f} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [f_0, \dots, f_{L-1}]^T$ collects the equalizer coefficients $f_m \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} f[m]$ and the p linearly independent vectors $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_p$ span the aforementioned kernel; these latter can be evaluated performing a singular value decomposition of the coefficient matrix of the linear system (8). When additive noise is present this solution has to be intended in a least squares sense.

It is worth noting that in (8) the modulation redundancy is directly exploited in the ZF equalizer coefficients. This has been made possible considering the fact that the ZF equalizer is found inside the class of FIR filters that reconstructs a sequence periodic modulo π from the transformed observations $z[n]$.

Now, in order to build the transformed observations $z[n]$, the knowledge of the zero ISI filter $d[n]$, congruent with a ZF equalizer according to (6), is needed. Here we observe only that the (spectrum of the) zero ISI filter $d_0[n]$ associated to the Wiener (Minimum Mean Squared Error) ZF equalizer admits the following expression

$$D_0(e^{j\omega}) = \frac{|H(e^{j\omega})|^2 / P_v(e^{j\omega})}{|H(e^{j\omega})|^2 / P_v(e^{j\omega}) + |H(e^{j\omega+j\pi})|^2 / P_v(e^{j\omega+j\pi})}$$

where $P_v(e^{j\omega})$ is the power spectral density of the noise. We remark that $D_0(e^{j\omega})$ can be consistently estimated from second order moments (time-varying correlations) of the received signal assuming the knowledge (within a scale factor) of the power spectral densities of the noise stochastic process.

A complete discussion of how it is possible to complete characterize the class of zero ISI filters $d[n]$ satisfying (6) goes beyond the scope of this contribution, and it is currently under investigation.

4. MODULATION REDUNDANCY DRIVEN ANALYTICAL CONSTANT MODULUS

Let us consider the equalizer parameterization (9) obtained by exploiting the modulation redundancy, now rewritten in a compact form as $\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{B} \boldsymbol{\alpha}$.

Since $\phi \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{f} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{f}} = (\mathbf{B} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{B}})(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \otimes \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})$, substituting in (4) yields

$$\mathcal{C}_y \mathcal{B} \boldsymbol{\gamma} = \mathbf{r}_y \quad (10)$$

where $\mathcal{B} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{B} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \boldsymbol{\alpha} \otimes \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}$, and $\otimes$ denotes the Kronecker product. Note that useful solutions of (10) must still be constrained as $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \boldsymbol{\alpha} \otimes \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}$. Then we may consider again the technique described in [6] to find them if the condition of having a number of linearly independent, constrained solution equal to the nullity of the system matrix $\mathcal{C}_y \mathcal{B}$ plus 1 is assured.

To this, we have the following

PROPOSITION 2

*Under the identifiability condition for the composite channel $(h * d^\pi)[n]$, the number of linearly independent, constrained solutions to system (10) is equal to the nullity of $\mathcal{C}_y \mathcal{B}$ plus 1.*

Proof: see [13].

Proposition (2) assures that the equalizer parameterization (9) allows to solve the analytical CM problem using the procedure given in [6].

Let us remark that the dimensionality of the analytical constant modulus approach has been reduced to p^2 where p is typically an odd integer ranging from 3 to 5, rarely 7, and the closed form solution is computable by algorithms of reasonable complexity.

5. RESULTS

Some numerical results, concerning with the measured microwave channels available at SPIB database (<http://spib.rice.edu>), are shown in Figs.2-3.

We have compared the performance of the analytical CM algorithm with performance of the SE iterative batch algorithm, because, as well known, this latter performs better than the CM iterative batch algorithm.

The results refers to the Mean Square Error (MSE) measured at the output of a FIR equalizer of $L = 12$ coefficients in the case of transmitted symbols drawn from a 8-PSK constellation. The signal-to-noise ratio, measured at the equalizer input, is 25 dB.

The analytical CM algorithm employs an equalizer parameterization of dimension $p = 5$, namely the dimension of the kernel of the 12×12 coefficient matrix in (8), while the solution of the system (10) is obtained through the procedure of [6] using a Super Generalized Schur Decomposition that works on a linear subspace of dimension 3.

Let us remark that the performance comparison refer to channels having a significant time-spread (the impulse responses span more that 25 samples) while the equalizer length is kept enough short in order to maintain an acceptable computational burden. This in turn implies that the model mismatch associated in the FIR approximation of the ISI free filter $D_0(e^{j\omega})$ is not negligible, and this explains the gain shown by the SE algorithm for large sample sizes. For this reason, the analytical CM algorithm is expected to perform better and better as the equalizer length increases.

Finally, let us remark that the analytical CM algorithm does not suffer, in principle, of any misconvergence problem, since it obtains the equalizer in a closed form. Thus the SE algorithm, or any other iterative one, can be usefully initialized by the analytical CM solution; in this respect, in many numerical experiments concerning with different channel typologies, we have experienced improved convergence in terms of number of iterations.

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Fig. 2: MSE at equalizer output vs. the number of received samples N ($SNR=25dB$, 8-PSK, SPIB channel MW-1).

Fig. 3: MSE at equalizer output vs. the number of received samples N ($SNR=25dB$, 8-PSK, SPIB channel MW-2).

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